

Strategy Management and Leadership at Chaos in Organizations

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Abstract: *The future reference on the technology age and strategic plans serve as an accelerator in the phenomenon at chaos. Chaos phenomenon makes the concept of planning meaningless and contradicts with the process of strategic management. The prediction that both the necessary and risky game that we play from now on about our future is the main problem in our study on the paradox of the strategic management approach. Within this framework, the perspective called Strategy Management and Leadership, Strategic Chaos Management Approach" is being discussed as a new alternative point of view to our study.*

Key Words: *Chaos, Organization, Strategy, Leadership, Strategy Management and Leadership, Leadership, Strategic Chaos Management.*

1. Introduction

Change is the concept that has a great impact to our era in the information age. This change, faced by today's leaders is greater and wider than ever. Globalization, rapidly evolving technology, changes in the structure of society and the increasing expectations also affect risk and crisis management forms.

The innovations and global environment, via information age, have revealed new threat entities rather than well known classic threats. Uncertainty itself is a very serious threat than ever has been. Sustaining the peace of communities and individuals necessitate good analysis of uncertainty and detection of crisis before approaching.

Today, leadership has become more complex than a simple leader-follower relationship in the environment which competition has become a part of the life, employee morale and satisfaction contributes to organization's efficiency and effectiveness and benefitting from the knowledge, skills and abilities has become the precious resource.

Showing the distinction of being a social phenomenon, "leadership" like all other social elements are affected and renewed by the change. Extensively studied, researched in experimental settings and quite popular, it is evaluated fairly normal that leadership shows development and helps gain new approaches in the literature. The works done to create leadership approach, in harmony with the characteristics of the information age, has led to the emergence of new leadership approaches.

Rapid changes in today's organizations are creating value. The future of the organizations, depend on their ability to adapt to developing conditions. This can be done with management which supports the flow of information. (Altıntaş,2001:7).

This article aims to evaluate contemporary events by understanding crisis and leadership notion and examining strategic leadership and distinct management approaches.

2. Crisis and Its Scope

The concept of crisis is not a new one and it has been there since the existence of the nation. In other words, the word of crisis goes back to Plato period. It appeared firstly in the shape of Krinein. Crisis means judging. In the subsequent period, it was used to mean separate and then decide. Gradually, crisis, meaning judgement and decision in Latin, transformed to Crisin in the 14th century and then Crisis and Crise in the 16th century¹.

Crisis, considering its components, exists when there is uncertainty. In particular, crises have become more frequent globally compared to recent hundred years. International crisis, comprehends destabilizing events, behaviors and attitudes which involves more than two countries and likely to change the international balance². The crisis threatens national values by expanding across borders and it is a situation that should be answered rapidly. Accordingly, it is a situation with which decision-makers should keep their attention at the highest level.³

The response to the question of What is a crisis ? is "depression in a society, company or person" most general sense. Crises occur with the organism -related disorders for a person, however crises in the scope of the society originate from problems in the state administration. Apart from political, financial and manufacturing crises, companies may experience crises from various other causes. In other words, crisis develops by "production-consumption imbalance" or it is "instability due to the disharmony between real sector of the economy and financial sector"⁴.

Nowadays, the impact of globalization on rich and poor separation increased, population movements and world trade accelerated, hunger, illegal immigration, piracy, human trafficking, domestic problems,

¹ ÇAKMAK, p.33.

² ÇAKMAK ,ibid. s.56

³ ÖZTÜRK, p.137

⁴ ALTUĞ, p.38.

environmental pollution and mass destruction weapons have become international issues. Criminal organizations associated with these problem areas have emerged as a threat to peace and security.

It is possible to collect crisis properties on three tiers.⁵ These properties are to threaten priorities of decision-makers, to reduce time and to perplex decision-makers in unexpected conditions.

Crises environment can provide very favorable conditions for the emergence of new leaders and talent in overcoming them. Weber's hypothesis that "crisis periods can provide very favorable conditions for the emergence of new leaders" is relevant with organizations which do business in an environment of crisis⁶. For instance, Atatürk is a charismatic leader who led to the revival of the nation during the crisis period.

3. Leadership and Its Scope

Leadership can be defined as a process that one individual affects and canalizes others in order to perform specific individual or group goals under certain conditions.

However, influencing is related with power supplies (authority, power) of the leader.⁷ Leadership is a process associated with the his or her activities.

It is possible to explain leadership process in the following function.⁸ It is; **Leadership =f(Leader, Viewers, Conditions)**. In other words, the leadership process is a complex relation between leaders, viewers and conditions.

Principles -based leadership is administered through four levels from the inside out.⁹ These are;

- Personal (relationship with oneself),
- Interpersonal (relationships and interactions with others),
 - Administrative (the responsibility to execute a job along with others),
 - Institutional (organizing people, collecting, training, rewarding, building teams, solving problems, building appropriate structures, strategies, and systems).

Leadership is an art. In a real sense, under certain circumstances and conditions, it is to influence the behaviors and actions of others. ATATURK is a great leader who achieved Turkish War of Independence and Revolution, the most comprehensive "change" and "transformation" in Turkish history.

Douglas Mc.Gregori, in his book of "The Human Side of Enterprise", focused on four variables of leadership¹⁰. These variables indicate characteristics of the leader, behaviour of follower, needs and personal characteristics, purpose, property of the organization in the context of its structure and its functions and the feature of social, economic and political environment.

"Self-recognition" of the leaders, in a crisis situation, will make them effective in management. The basis of this lies in that leaders have realistic idea about themselves as individuals. Fulfilling following issues will benefit the leader in effective management¹¹.

- Implement warning systems to detect signals of crisis,
- Identification and removal of weak points in terms of institution's performance,
- Talking to their subordinates about the importance of teamwork and unity,
- Highlighting that the success belongs to the entire team especially when effective and efficient results achieved.

Ultimately, leadership is the fundamental element for good management. It is to enable an environment that work is done because employees want it be done not because management wants it be done¹². Leadership is the ability to influence people to perform for the goals of the institution. It is the the atmosphere and a set of synergies leaders have created in the workplace.

4. Strategic Management and Leadership

Strategy has definitions such as "a way to achieve the predetermined goal"¹³ and "a battle management information". Kaplan and Norton, who have signed important works in this subject, considers strategy the steps taken as a whole in a continuous manner and they evaluate that leadership is a process that needs to be developed constantly¹⁴.

The strategic management, founded on strategy, "is a process that enables long-term viability, competitive edge and above average profit" rather than the management of the organization's routine and ordinary affairs.

In our time, in order to keep pace with the rapid changes, visionary management and leadership should look not only indoors, but also to outside world in the same ratio. Change, adaptation to change and the ability to manage change are prominent concepts in strategic management approaches. Change is a process which is

⁵ ÇAKMAK ,ibid.,p.34.

⁶ BRAYMAN,p.54-55.

⁷ KOÇEL,p.445.

⁸ KOÇEL,ibid ,p.448.

⁹ COVEY, p.15

¹⁰ TÜRKEL, p.95

¹¹ ÇELİK, p.80.

¹² ADAİR, p.105.

¹³ Türk Dil Kurumu, Turkish Dictionary, p.1811

¹⁴ GÜROL & KILIÇLIOĞLU, p.882.

acquired over time and differentiates existing features and qualities in a continuous manner.

It is a crucial success criteria that organizations manage their environment to cope with adaptation to change and competition.

One of the main objectives of the organization is to render organizational life steady, to analyze uncertainty and to predict whether a crisis is soon to happen.

It is not possible to analyze such a work environment and solve its inherent problems with conventional management principles and theories.

If there is not a crisis period, one can not talk about a rescuer leader. ATATÜRK is the person who defined the nation's will as supreme and created the power, called erk, irresistible force with Amasya Circular¹⁵.

A workplace in a crisis can bring about some problems. With the implementation of the conventional methods during crisis, stress, tension, pressure, imbalance, ill-considered decisions and problems are likely to arise.

Such an institution will begin to disintegrate in the end¹⁶. Leadership skills in the management of this process is vital for the institution, namely, the institution's staying alive is parallel with the success of the leader.

5. Strategic Crisis (Chaos) Management

In today's conjuncture, institutions have become crucial with the increasing importance of phenomena such as change, adaptation to change and ability to manage change, uncertainty, risk, crisis and chaos. The companies, eager to survive, should diversify beyond routine practice, pursue innovation and have future projections.

In this environment, decision-makers have two options to find the balance in a crisis: To find the balance before any crisis takes place or to find the balance with a change resulting from the crisis¹⁷.

In this context; it is crucial for success that leaders perceive the crisis accurately, care about it, see the picture as a whole and do analyze crisis comprehensively to determine its dimensions and implement the remedial action plan decisively.

Including international security organizations and countries, the recommendation of "**Strategic Crisis (Chaos) Management Approach**", considered proper for the management all kinds of organizations currently,

is designed to turn strategic management-chaos paradox into an opportunity.

Strategic Crisis Management approach suggests that crisis is intertwined with the strategic management process and the paradoxical relationship between them can be used.

In this context, the interaction between the strategic management process and chaos is offered as chaos strategic management awareness.

In this interaction, strategic management is accepted as an important tool in managing crisis phenomenon. However, in this model crisis management is a partial management and it is not stated that chaos can be managed completely. This partial idea of manageability is seen as an important initiative for strategic management.

Strategic crisis management approach suggests that strategic management process would be more efficient under the circumstances of stable equilibrium. However, this management approach defends the necessity of prevention efforts during chaos processes in which limited instability reign.

During explosive instability, this approach concentrates on crisis prevention efforts, the most appropriate behavior for strategy makers. Strategic Crisis Management approach proposes two main approaches to manage the chaos: Create a crisis and prevent the crisis. The idea of creating the crisis, which should be evaluated at every stage of the strategic management process, is envisaged as the most basic approach for the prevention of chaos.

This approach, projected to be used in the future, should be an important tool for creative strategic leaders. Controlled uncontrol is a dynamic creativity and it is seen as an important approach for strategic leaders in managing chaos and enabling strategic management.

The following principles can provide solution to community crises with regard to crisis management.¹⁸

- Leaders should be familiar with the members of the group and trust them.
 - Each crisis should be taken on its own terms, not on personal reactions, and be focused on the team integrity.
- Team unity should be emphasized at every opportunity when there is chance to succeed.
- Focus on staff morale.
- After the diagnosis of the problem, it should be considered whether it can be resolved over time or not.
- Staff should take participate in decision making and implementation.

¹⁵ ÖZDEMİR, p.2-3.

¹⁶ SILVER, p.63.

¹⁷ ÇAKMAK, ibid, p.35.

¹⁸ SABUNCUOĞLU & TÜZ, p.190.

- When change of attitudes needed, instead of threat positive reinforcement should be provided.
- Control feelings during a crisis especially when anger and anxiety prevails.
- Employees should be observed about their reactions to the event.
- Leader should never lose authority in a crisis.

It is essential that an effective leader be visionary , life-long learner, honest, frank, tolerant and set an example by encouraging others. Moreover, leaders should be instructive, facilitator, a guide and motivator to lead the masses.

During the crisis, the leaders carrying out leadership role strengthen their role within the group. The resulting penetration of the group will play an important role in mobilizing the group. It is important that leaders should not be alarmed, act in a systematic manner and to negotiate with other managers¹⁹.

6. Conclusion

With uncertainties in the global environment, speed and change in the information age affects society, institutions and individuals. In addition, features of leaders and organizations do change facilities and the environment. This situation renders it mandatory to have effective leadership skills to see the picture as a whole . During and after the Independence War, Atatürk 's strategy and his diplomacy is an example of an effective leadership.

It is possible to exist in the future by managing the future. However, organizations overlook ensuring the future. In this context, measures to be taken at the macro level are given below:²⁰

Beyond national security, global security strategies should be planned and implemented earnestly. While strategic planning within the framework of international security, steps should be taken according to crisis prerequisites.

All kinds of organizations should support the development of the environment to their own benefit. On a global scale the weak link should be supported at a sufficient level . It is required that institutions internalize the concepts of control , competition, flexibility and innovation including R & D activities.

As long as the technological innovations, developing countries deal with, are perceived as normal at our present level of consciousness limit of chaos can not be exceeded and can not be surpassed beyond

becoming a part of the process. Therefore, innovation approaches should be evaluated by a new vision.

There is no method to completely eliminate the possibility of crisis . Such an environment will not be able to overcome conventional management rules. However, the micro level measures to be taken to exit from the crisis are;

- Effective leadership,
- Corporate Reorganizations,
- To determine the factors that caused the crisis calmly,
- To take corrective measures in the long run,
 - To make flexible and contingent plans as response to for possible crises in the future.

In conclusion, leaders who are unable to follow the change will lack in guiding and managing crises. In addition, crisis management will be vital for future managers , institutions and communities regarding the resistance to change and increasing conflict in the world.

Therefore, crises can be prevented, solved and turned into opportunities by the help of effective leadership, proper flow of crisis management system, teamwork and synergistic collaboration.

Summary

The future reference on the technology age and strategic plans serve as an accelerator in the phenomenon at chaos. Chaos phenomenon makes the concept of planning meaningless and contradicts with the process of strategic management. The prediction that both the necessary and risky game that we play from now on about our future is the main problem in our study on the paradox of the strategic management approach. Within this framework, the perspective called "Strategy Management and Leadership, Strategic Chaos Management Approach" is being discussed as a new alternative point of view to our study.

When security is associated with "risk and threat", there is a complex relationship among risk, threat and security. These two concepts are frequently used as common phrases in discourse and literature. In this study, of the notions of "risk and threat" taken as corollaries, "risk" and its projection on "risk management" are analyzed distinctively.

Upon evaluating the studies on risk and risk management, it is understood that there is no unity in the approaches to 'risk'. Among scholars, the studies regarding risk are classified in two groups: While the fields of study like finance, banking, insurance,

¹⁹ COLEMAN,,p.166-167.

²⁰ TURUNÇ, p.68-69

statistics, and combating natural disasters based on mathematical calculations of probability can be considered under the first group; in the light of the social developments, the studies based on socio-cultural and psychological approaches and security studies can be perceived within second group.

When the security studies are evaluated, it is noticed that the meaning attached to the concept of risk resembles that which corresponds to the concept of risk perceived in finance, banking, insurance, and statistics. However, the similarity or distinction in the use of the term affects the structure of security and risk management directly. In this progress, *Leadership* is very important factor.

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